

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE DESIGN AND ANALYSIS: MESH COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE WITH GAMIFIED SOCIAL COLLABORATION TO STRENGTHEN CYBERSECURITY AWARENESS

MAYKIN WARASART¹, PALLOP PIRIYASURAWONG²

Division of Information and Communication Technology for Education, Faculty of Technical Education,

King Mongkut's University of Technology North Bangkok, Bangkok, Thailand

E-mail: ¹maykin@iecee.org, ¹maykin@owasp.org, ²pallop.p@fte.kmutnb.ac.th

ABSTRACT

Cybersecurity awareness remains a major challenge due to the evolving nature of cyber threats and the difficulty of sustaining employees' engagement in traditional training programs. To address this problem, the concept of a mesh community of practice is introduced to be an effective way to increase collaborative awareness and empower the workforce to be better prepared by keeping pace with the latest threats and mitigation practices. In this research, the authors aim to design an architecture of mesh community of practice driven by social collaboration and gamification for cybersecurity awareness enhancement and evaluate the designed architecture. The study began by stating the designed architecture, followed by an evaluation that was based on expert judgment conducted by ten subject matter experts who have related experiences from various organizations. These experts assess and verify the appropriateness of the designed system architecture. The evaluation results indicated that the proposed design (individual component) was rated highest level (mean=4.62, S.D.=0.48), and was also rated highest level (mean=4.58, S.D.=0.69) for entire system, respectively. The findings indicate that the proposed architecture can effectively enhance awareness and engagement, offering a practical model for continuous cybersecurity learning.

Keywords: *Cybersecurity Awareness, Gamification, Mesh Community of Practice, Social Collaboration*

1. INTRODUCTION

Cyber threats are not only evolving; they are also escalating [1]. The global average cost of a data breach increased to \$4.88 million in 2024, marking a 10% rise from 2023—representing the largest annual increase since the pandemic [2]. Account takeovers and fraud are being driven by more than 100 billion compromised records [3]. Organizations must prepare their workforces for increased data security and cybersecurity efforts [4]. Unfortunately, there is a global shortage of more than 4 million cyber professionals [5]. It is crucial to establish employee immunity through awareness-raising, as security is the responsibility of all, encompassing the individuals in the non-technical disciplines who are experiencing difficulty in maintaining their security, thereby introducing new attack vectors for cybercriminals [6]. Traditional training approaches often fail to sustain engagement or adapt to rapidly changing threat landscapes, which underscores the need for a more dynamic,

participatory, and scalable solution. The use of community of practice and gamification to drive the movement is therefore proposed [7]. to strengthen defenses to block human-targeted attacks today. This approach is expected to improve user participation, foster peer learning, and encourage continuous awareness development. The system architecture is vital because it will be the input or blueprint for the system development phase, and the quality of the input will be determined by the quality of the system architecture design.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- To design the system architecture of mesh community of practice with gamified social collaboration to strengthen cybersecurity awareness.
- To evaluate the appropriateness of the designed system architecture of mesh community of practice with gamified social collaboration to strengthen cybersecurity awareness.

3. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

3.1. Mesh CoP

The concept of mesh community of practice (or Mesh CoP, MCoP) has proposed by [7]. which is applied the Gartner’s Mesh theme [8]. that refers to the dynamic interconnection of people, processes, things, and services, which results in major changes in user experience, supporting technology and platform, of the community of practice, to be the evolved version of VCoP introduced by [9], [10].

3.1.1 Conversational System/Platform

Conversational System/Platform or Chatbot has a number of advantages over traditional user interfaces. The user can interface directly with the information system and request the information they require [11].

3.1.2 Mesh app and service architecture (MASA)

MASA is becoming a disruptive force due to its expansion, which necessitates the integration of these disparate endpoints into a unified whole. Mobile applications, web applications, and other applications rapidly connect to this web of back-end services [12].

resilience and scale through horizontal scaling, distributed computing, and automated component replacement [13].

3.1.4 Digital Technology Platform

Digital Technology Platform refers to an area that is developed on the ideas and architecture of services. The purpose is to provide an interoperable set of services that may be used to create apps, processes, and other applications. As a result, a platform is formed by a symbiotic collection of technology capabilities and components [14].

3.1.5 Adaptive Security Architecture (ASA),

ASA, as systems become increasingly sophisticated over time and the nature of security threats changes, a continuous, contextual, and coordinated approach is essential to maintain security. ASA should be used to monitor and resolve any security issues in the system or platform continuously [15].

3.2. Gamified Social collaboration

Social collaboration, together with the gamification concept, so-called gamified social collaboration, is used to accelerate a group of people

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework (Created by the author)

3.1.3 Cloud native

For today's corporate landscape, many organizations/companies migrate their on-premises applications, workloads, and data to the cloud because it is a big game-changer and provides exceptional flexibility, functionality, and speed to many enterprises. Cloud Native, also known as “architecting for the cloud”, focuses on attaining

who share the same interest to work together to efficiently achieve a common goal. It also makes the learning environment more enjoyable [16].

3.3. Cybersecurity Awareness

The business revolves around data. Almost every industry now has a tremendous shift in data requirements. Downtime prevention, security, reliability, and cost savings are all important aspects

of data security, especially personal data [17]. It has been argued that data is the new oil, and in the new data-based economy, personal data or personally identifiable information (PII) is being drilled for. Cybersecurity awareness includes finding, fixing, and preventing security vulnerability in humans.

Despite various awareness programs, organizations continue to suffer from human-factor breaches, indicating a persistent problem in engaging users and sustaining behavioral change. The lack of social reinforcement, relevance, and interactivity in traditional methods remains a critical gap. Similar studies have examined gamification in cybersecurity awareness, such as phishing simulations and serious game [18]. However, most focus on content delivery rather than sustained peer engagement. Our design approach adopts a community-driven perspective, grounded in social collaboration and gamification, and validated through expert evaluation.

- Phase 1: Design the system architecture and create an instrument for assessing the appropriateness of the designed system architecture.
- Phase 2: Evaluate the appropriateness of the proposed designed system architecture by obtaining the arithmetic mean and standard deviation via the created research instrument from the sample of ten highly experienced experts in the field of information and communication technology and higher education institutes for at least 5 years.

5. RESULTS

The system architecture allowed us to break the system down and describe components/modules, interfaces between these components/modules, and interactions with the environment, and the behavior of components is linked to the services they provide,

Figure 2: System architecture of the mesh community of practice with gamified social collaboration

The conceptual framework of mesh community of practice with gamified social collaboration to strengthen cybersecurity awareness derived from [7], is shown in Figure 1.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

and these services rely on data that must be identified and described [19], [20]. The system architecture proposed in this study is depicted in Figure 2. It is divided into 4 main components: 1) Community of Practice, Conversational System/Platform, Mesh CoP Management, and the Supporting Services, respectively.

This architectural design is also concerned with the [12], in which the primary objective is to achieve learning outcomes for the community of

Figure 3: The use case internal the Mesh CoP Management

practice both in business organizations and the educational world, while we are in the hybrid working/learning environment where almost everyone tends to go remote-first. The office workers, learners, or students have greater mobility today than they have ever had before [21], it is the

We are able to use their applications both on mobile devices and on computers to communicate together.

The conversational system/platforms to choose should be: 1) Lightweight due to mobile devices not having a lot of memory or processing power [23], even though they are using the rich

Table 1: Description of the relationship between the use case and the actor

Use Case	Actor	Description
Create campaign	Community Leader(s)	The starting point of each iteration period
Add rewards	Community Sponsor(s)	To create motivations, usually come from executives
Add members	Community Leader(s) & Members	Incorporate new members into the community
Make conversation	Community Leader(s) & Members	Focus on conversations about cybersecurity
Add rich content	Community Leader(s)	Create quizzes, knowledge base for members using the rich menu feature of the conversational system/platform
Access rich content	Community Leader(s) & Members	Use the knowledge base, take quizzes to collect points
Give score	Community Leader(s) & Members	Give points to those who contribute to the community
View leaderboard	Community Leader(s) & Members	Who got how many points? How much progress has been made?
Promote new leader	Community Leader(s)	People who are ready to expand their cycle

reason why Instant Messaging, or IM [22], is the best way ever for the community’s members to communicate together. Many conversational systems/platforms now enable us to send instant messages of various input types, such as text, both from typing or using the speech to text feature, images, stickers, location, video clips and sounds.

menus to interact with the community members. 2) Simple and easy to use to maintain user familiarity and the limitations of the devices' screens to facilitate learning comprehension [24].

The interaction between the Community of Practice’s members, Conversational System and Mesh CoP Management is as follows: 1) When

members of the Community of Practice send the messages or use the rich menu feature (via the Community Touchpoint: mobile phones, tablets, or PCs), the messages or the information associated with the rich menu's content is sent to the members via the Conversational System/Platform. 2) The Conversational System/Platform sends a message via webhook event to the webhook URL [25] of the Mesh CoP Management, which is hosted on the cloud server. 3) The Mesh CoP Management may call the REST API provided by the Conversational System/Platform or perform any other processing based on the content of the webhook event. 4) The Conversational System/Platform will either send a message to the Community of Practice based on the content of the REST API call, or it will switch the rich menu displayed to the Community of Practice to another one that has been pre-programmed.

The Mesh CoP Management is the core of the Mesh Community of Practice and consists of Gamified Social Collaboration Management Module (the gamification driven by social collaboration), Community Knowledge Management Module (to delivery cybersecurity contents to the members),

based form [26], which has a responsive design [27] for mobile devices, to collect the learning progress of the community's members. Also, the feature for giving a reward to the members is valuable. We can use it to receive the recommended content from the members to share in the community as well. The reward, contents, member's information, and learning progress of community members can be kept in the cloud storage, both cloud databases and cloud-based spreadsheets [28], which have restricted access. The Notification Service [29] can be used to send alerts about the periodic learning progress measurement, the member ranking in the community leaderboard, newly released content, and so on by creating a related condition in the storage [30]. The rise of sophisticated attackers has necessitated the need for businesses to comprehend, promptly respond to, and hunt down the most sophisticated threats inside their organizations. Cyber Threat Intelligence, or CTI [31], [32] can be used via External API for both the nearly real-time content for the community. To make the conversational response to the members nearly real-time like humans, by immediately returning the information

Table 2: The Gartner's Mesh theme characteristic achievement

Characteristic	Achieved by
Conversational System/Platform	The well-known platforms such as Chatbot Platform [35], [36], etc.
Mesh App & Service Architecture	The main features are the mobile application and the desktop app, and modern web browsers support extensions and plugins.
Cloud Native	The Mesh CoP Management Engine can host and run on a cloud server like [37], which is able to call other cloud native services.
Digital Technology Platform	Supporting Services is constantly working to improve the customer experience.
Adaptive Security Architecture (ASA)	Calling the CTI to be the source of threat information to be the nearly real-time KBs. They can also be used in the ASA prediction phase

Member Management Module (community member directory), and Measurement Management Module (for measuring the progress of members), which is reflected in the internal use cases with 3 actors: community sponsors, community leaders, and community members, as in Figure 3 and the description in Table 1.

The Supporting Services are the related services to support the Mesh CoP Management Engine, consisting of the Cloud Document, Cloud Storage, Notification Service, Generative AI, Automated Script, and any external APIs. Once the community is started, the community leader sets up the rules and is able to communicate with the community using text messages because the community leader is also a community member. Cloud-based document services can be used as a means of data entry for community members in the event of sending messages to the conversational platform, which is not suitable. We can use a cloud-

from the knowledge base, generation AI like [33] or [34] can also be used as a community chatbot for participating with community members while the community leaders are unavailable, such as after midnight or having a meeting.

The proposed system architecture aligns with Gartner's Mesh theme [8], which the authors use as the referenced model, as shown in Table 2.

The appropriateness evaluation criteria for determining the range are split into five levels according to the Likert scale, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean score range and interpretation of results

Score Range	Meaning of Values
4.50 – 5.00	The highest level of appropriateness
3.50 – 4.49	The high level of appropriateness
2.50 – 3.49	The moderate level of appropriateness
1.50 – 2.49	The low level of appropriateness
1.00 – 1.49	The lowest level of appropriateness

Table 4: Results of the evaluation of individual component

Evaluation items		Mean	S.D.	Level of Appropriateness
Community of Practice	Community Members & Touchpoint	4.70	0.48	Highest
Conversational System	Community Engine with Text & Graphic	4.70	0.48	Highest
Mesh CoP Management	Gamified Social Collaboration Management	4.90	0.32	Highest
	Community Knowledge Management	4.80	0.42	Highest
	Member Management	4.60	0.52	Highest
Supporting Services	Measurement Management	4.80	0.42	Highest
	Cloud Document	4.40	0.52	High
	Cloud Storage	4.70	0.48	Highest
	Notification Service	4.40	0.52	High
	Generative AI	4.50	0.53	Highest
	Automated Script	4.40	0.52	High
	External API	4.50	0.53	Highest
Summary of evaluation		4.62	0.48	Highest

Table 5: Results of the evaluation of the appropriateness of the entire system architecture

Evaluation items	Mean	S.D.	Level of Appropriateness
The architecture that has been designed is in accordance with the research objectives.	4.50	0.71	Highest
The components of the architecture that have been designed display a clear hierarchy that is progressive.	4.50	0.71	Highest
The system architecture's component arrangement was both comprehensible and appropriate.	4.80	0.63	Highest
All the system architecture's components are fully functional and satisfy the specifications.	4.50	0.71	Highest
Summary of evaluation	4.58	0.69	Highest

From Table 4, it is found that the designed system architecture (individual component), experts have commented that the appropriateness of the designed system architecture is highest appropriated for all components. Including Community Members & Touchpoint (mean=4.70 and S.D.=0.48), Text and Graphic conversations (mean=4.70 and S.D.=0.48), the Gamified Social Collaboration (mean=4.90, S.D.=0.32), Community Knowledge Management (mean=4.80 and S.D.=0.42), Member Management (mean=4.60, S.D.=0.52), Measurement (mean=4.80 and S.D.=0.42), the Cloud Document (mean=4.40, S.D.=0.52), Cloud Storage (mean=4.70, S.D.=0.48), the Notification Service (mean=4.40, S.D.=0.52), Generative AI (mean=4.50, S.D.=0.53), Automated Script (mean=4.40 and S.D.=0.52), and the External API (mean=4.50, S.D.=0.53).

The results of appropriateness evaluation for individual components of the system architecture were overall at the highest level, with a mean of 4.62 and a standard deviation of 0.48, which was in the range of 0 to 1. This could be considered reliable data, so it could be concluded that the experts with relatively similar opinions were at the highest level.

From Table 5, it is shown that the designed system architecture (individual component has the highest level of appropriateness (mean=4.58 and S.D.=0.69). Concluded that the designed system

architecture is able to be used as a blueprint for the development phase.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study are directly aligned with the stated research objectives. The first objective—to design the system architecture of a mesh community of practice with gamified social collaboration—was achieved through the development of a structured architecture comprising four essential components: 1) Community of Practice, 2) Conversational System/Platform, 3) MCoP Management, and 4) Supporting Services.

The second objective—to evaluate the appropriateness of the designed architecture—was accomplished through expert judgment by ten professionals in ICT and higher education. The overall results showed that 1) the appropriateness of the designed system architecture (for individual component) is the highest appropriated (mean=4.62, S.D.=0.48) and 2) the appropriateness of designed system architecture (for entire system) is the highest appropriated (mean=4.58, S.D.=0.69), respectively.

While the expert validation confirms the theoretical soundness and design relevance, the study is limited by the absence of real-world deployment and empirical user feedback. Further

work should include pilot implementation and behavioral impact assessments to measure actual improvements in cybersecurity awareness.

Compared to state-of-the-art solutions such as phishing simulations, and serious game, the proposed architecture distinguishes itself by combining gamification with community-driven collaboration—offering a more holistic, scalable, and socially reinforced approach. Overall, the designed architecture serves as a practical and theoretically grounded blueprint for development phase, capable of addressing the persistent gaps in current cybersecurity awareness initiatives.

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